

Comparison of the Seismic Performance of Conventional Moment Resisting Frames and Innovative Dissipative Replaceable Link Frames

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Abstract. The Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame (DRLF) is an innovative lateral load resisting system, recently developed, investigated, and further optimized in the European research projects FUSEIS, MATCH, INNOSEIS and DISSIPABLE. The system consists of two strong columns, which are rigidly interconnected by several horizontal beams, forming a vertical VIERENDEEL beam. The interconnecting beams are attached by bolted end-plate connections, making them easily detachable. These links are separated from the slab; consequently, they do not take part in the gravity load bearing function. The dissipative replaceable links being the only intended spots of inelastic action and therefore energy dissipation act as replaceable seismic fuses during a strong earthquake. After such an event, exchanging the beam links is foreseen to restore the structure to its undamaged pre-earthquake conditions quickly. Thus, the structure must possess sufficient re-centring capabilities. Recently an improvement of the initial DRLF system has been introduced within the DISSIPABLE research project: i.e. DRLF's joined by means of strong coupling beams, forming a Coupled Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame (CDRLF). These coupling beams are not intended to dissipate energy, but instead should remain elastic, in order to provide a source of re-centring. In this paper the basic concept of the DRLF and CDRLF is introduced and demonstrated by applying it to the design of a typical low- and mid-rise office building. The case study includes also two traditional Moment Resisting Frames (MRF). A rough cost comparison is made based on steel consumption, and the seismic performance of both strategies is investigated via non-linear static analyses. In comparison to MRF's it is shown, how the CDRLF approach is better suited for modern performance driven seismic design, focusing on reparability and cost effectiveness.

Keywords: dissipative replaceable link frame (DRLF), coupled dissipative replaceable link frame (CDRLF), dissipative replaceable beam links, re-centring capability, performance-based design.

1 Introduction

The Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame (DRLF) is an innovative lateral load resisting system, which was initially developed and investigated in the European research project “FUSEIS - dissipative devices for seismic-resistant steel frames” [1]. The objective of the FUSEIS project was to overcome the drawback of non-repairability of traditional systems such as Moment Resisting Frames (MRF), Concentrically Braced Frames (CBF) or Eccentrically Braced Frames (EBF). Such conventional systems perform well during strong seismic events due to dissipation of a large amount of energy, however, they are not economically repairable after the design basis earthquake has struck the structure. Thus, usually the only available option is the demolishing of the damaged building and replacing it by a new one. To overcome this issue, several innovative systems have been developed within the FUSEIS project, where the dissipative elements called fuses are the only source of energy dissipation, and above all, are easily replaceable after an earthquake.

One of the investigated systems was the formerly called FUSEIS-1 system (see [1], [2], [3]), which in this paper is called Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame (DRLF). It was further developed and investigated within the MATCH [4] and INNOSEIS [5] projects, and is further enhanced within the on-going DISSIPABLE [6] project.

The DRLF system consists of two strong columns, which are rigidly interconnected by several beams, forming a vertical VIERENDEEL beam. In order to be easily detachable, these interconnecting beams – the Dissipative Replaceable Links (DRL) – are attached by a bolted end-plate connection. As they are not coupled with the slab, they are not a part of the gravity load bearing frame. Optimally, inelastic action is foreseen to take place solely in the Dissipative Replaceable Links (DRL). When properly designed, they can act as exchangeable seismic fuses during a strong earthquake. Being the only source of energy dissipation by design, along with the missing participation in the gravity load bearing paths and moreover their detachable connection design, exchanging the Dissipative Replaceable Links is foreseen to restore the structure to its undamaged pre-earthquake stage quickly, without the need of rebuilding the whole structure.

Eurocode 8 [7] demands on damage limitation related to non-structural components – like e.g. partition walls – represent a tough requirement on global lateral stiffness of such Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame systems. For high buildings, displacement verifications often govern the design. In order to increase global stiffness, partial-strength moment connections may be introduced to the gravity load bearing frames, which are initially not intended to contribute to the lateral stiffness provided solely by the DRLF. However, this may result in damage of the gravity frame connections, which are usually not feasibly repairable, finally preventing full exploitation of the potentially excellent energy dissipation capacity of such a system.

In this paper, an alternative solution of increasing lateral stiffness of Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame systems is investigated – i.e. the connections of the gravity frames are kept as hinged, while strong elastic steel coupling beams are used to connect two Dissipative Replaceable Link Frames. These coupling beams are not intended to dissipate energy, but instead to remain elastic, in order to keep the whole build-

ing easily repairable, by restricting seismic damage to the DRLF fuses. In the following, a study of 4- and 8-storey office buildings is presented. An introduction to the innovative concept of the Coupled Dissipative Replaceable Link Frame (CDRLF) system was presented in detail within a previous work [8]. The gain in performance achieved by the introduction of the coupling beams is discussed in terms of capacity curves, plastic mechanisms, reparability and steel consumption. It is shown, how the CDRLF system is well able to comply with the foreseen performance targets.

2 Case study

A case study was defined and investigated considering the structural configuration with 4 and 8 stories illustrated in Fig. 1 as a starting point. Considering the floor layout and the perimeter lateral load resisting structure, it can be observed that the structural configurations are symmetric in the two orthogonal directions.

Fig. 1. Arrangement and dimensions (mm) of the structural configuration: floor layout (with columns, main beams and secondary beams); perimeter lateral load resisting structure

The structural configurations and in particularly the perimeter lateral load resisting frames of the case studies (see Fig. 2) are as follows: ▪ MRF – moment resisting frame (Fig. 2a-b); ▪ DRLF – dissipative replaceable link frame (Fig. 2c-d); ▪ CDRLF – coupled dissipative replaceable link frame (Fig. 2e-f).

Fig. 2. Perimeter lateral load resisting frames: (a)-(b) MRF; (c)-(d) DRLF; (e)-(f) CDRLF

The design of each frame configuration according to Fig. 2 was based on the following input: ▪ loading conditions (Table 1); ▪ seismic action parameters (Table 2); ▪ general properties of the 4- and 8-story frames (Table 3). The resulting cross-sections for the perimeter lateral load resisting frames are presented in Table 4 and Table 5.

Regarding the CDRLF, the use of coupling beams is a well-known concept for linking two RC walls, designing the coupling beams to dissipate energy (see e.g. [9]). In contrast, in the current study the aim of the coupling beams is to remain elastic for damage limitation (DL) and significant damage (SD) intensity earthquakes. To keep the coupling beams as long as possible in the elastic range, the connections were defined as “fixed” at one end and “pinned” at the other end (see Table 3), similar with the boundary conditions of the coupling beams from [10]. In addition, coupling beams at the lower stories were realised from S460 high strength steel. The investigated innovative system (CDRLF) could be best compared to dual frame systems, e.g. a combination of an EBF with a MRF, where the MRF is deemed to add not only stiffness and residual strength to the system – but also a re-centring capability, see e.g. [11].

Table 1. Loading conditions used for design

Design loads	Description	Load value
Dead loads	Composite slab and steel sheeting	2.75 kN/m ²
Superimposed loads	Services, ceiling and raised floor	0.75 kN/ m ²
	Perimeter walls	4.00 kN/m
Live loads	Offices (Class B)	3.00 kN/m ²
	Movable partitions	0.80 kN/m ²

Table 2. Seismic design action according to Eurocode 8

Seismic design action	Description
Peak ground acceleration (4-story frames)	$\alpha_{gR} = 0.30 \cdot g$
Peak ground acceleration (8-story frames)	$\alpha_{gR} = 0.36 \cdot g$
Importance factor (Class II)	$\gamma_1 = 1.0$
Ground type	B ($S = 1.2$, $T_B = 0.15$ s, $T_C = 0.5$ s, $T_D = 2.0$ s)
Type of response spectrum	Type 1
Lower bound factor	$\beta = 0.2$
Behaviour factor	$q = 5$

Table 3. General properties of the 4- and 8-story case study frames

Structural system	MRF	DRLF	CDRLF
Bays (4-story frames)	2 x 8 m	3 x (6+2 m)	1 x 8 m & 2 x (2+6 m)
Bays (8-story frames)	2 x 8 m	3 x (5.5+2.5 m)	1 x 8 m & 2 x (2.5+5.5 m)
Column base connection	fixed	pinned	pinned
Coupling beam connections	-	pinned	pinned-fixed

Table 4. Cross-sections of elements for the 4-story case study frames

Floor	MRF ($T_1=1.36$ sec.)		DRLF ($T_1=1.38$ sec.)		CDRLF ($T_1=1.38$ sec.)		Cpl. Beams
	Columns	Beams	Columns	Links*	Columns	Links*	
	S355	S235	S355	S235	S355	S235	S355/S460
4	HEB-500	IPE-400	HEA-400	HEA-200	HEA-400	HEA-200	HEB-320
3	HEB-500	IPE-500	HEA-400	HEA-220	HEA-400	HEA-220	HEB-340
2	HEB-500	IPE-550	HEA-400	HEA-220	HEA-400	HEA-240	HEB-360
1	HEB-500	IPE-550	HEA-400	HEA-240	HEA-400	HEA-260	HEB-400**

Note: * the dissipative zones of the links contain a reduced beam section (RBS)

** the coupling beams (CB) at the first story are realised from S460 steel grade

Table 5. Cross-sections of elements for the 8-story case study frames

Floor	MRF ($T_1=2.69$ sec.)		DRLF ($T_1=2.73$ sec.)		CDRLF ($T_1=2.75$ sec.)		Cpl. Beams
	Columns	Beams	Columns	Links*	Columns	Links*	
	S355	S235	S355	S235	S355	S235	S355/S460
8	HEA-500	IPE-400	HEA-400	HEA-260	HEA-400	HEA-200	HEB-360
7	HEA-500	IPE-450	HEA-400	HEA-260	HEA-400	HEA-200	HEB-360
6	HEA-500	IPE-500	HEA-400	HEA-260	HEA-400	HEA-200	HEB-360
5	HEA-500	IPE-550	HEA-400	HEA-260	HEA-400	HEA-220	HEB-400
4	HEB-500	IPE-550	HEB-400	HEA-260	HEB-400	HEA-240	HEB-400**
3	HEB-500	IPE-600	HEB-400	HEA-260	HEB-400	HEA-240	HEB-400**
2	HEB-500	IPE-600	HEB-400	HEA-260	HEB-400	HEA-260	HEB-400**
1	HEB-500	IPE-600	HEB-400	HEA-280	HEB-400	HEA-280	HEB-400**

Note: * the dissipative zones of the links contain a reduced beam section (RBS)

** the coupling beams (CB) at the first 4 stories are realised from S460 steel grade

3 Seismic performance

The seismic performance was evaluated through a set of nonlinear static analyses (pushover) using the N2 method [12]. In addition, the seismic performance of each 3D structural configuration is being investigated also through nonlinear dynamic (time-history) analyses using 2x7 spectrum compatible accelerograms. Both types of analyses were performed using SAP2000 [13]. The plastic hinge definitions for the Dissipative Replaceable Links were defined according to the parameters reported in [2], while the plastic hinge definitions of the other members are described in [8].

From the nonlinear static analyses, a set of capacity curves were obtained for both 4- and 8-story frames (see Fig. 3a, 3b). Further, the N2 method [12] was used to determine the target displacements given in Table 6 for each state of the structural systems corresponding to the three seismic intensity levels, i.e. DL (damage limitation), SD (significant damage), and NC (near collapse). Due to the similar fundamental periods of the structures, the initial stiffness of the capacity curves (see Fig. 3a, 3b) and the target displacements (see Table 6 and Fig. 3a, 3b) are very close to each other.

Table 6. Target displacements [m] corresponding to 4- and 8-story frames

Limit state	a_g/a_{gr}	MRF 4	DRLF 4	CDRLF 4	MRF 8	DRLF 8	CDRLF 8
DL	0.5	0.105	0.105	0.106	0.184	0.190	0.189
SD	1.0	0.210	0.209	0.211	0.368	0.380	0.377
NC	1.7	0.357	0.356	0.359	0.625	0.646	0.641

The nonlinear static analyses demonstrated the following: ▪ at DL intensity level all structural configurations were characterized by an elastic response; ▪ at SD intensity level – with the exception of the 8-story DRLF – all structural configurations were characterised by a nonlinear response with plastic hinges forming in dissipative zones (i.e. beams, links); ▪ at NC intensity level all structural configurations were characterised by a nonlinear response and a global plastic mechanism (see Fig. 3c, 3d). The inter-story drifts were observed to be within the codified limits. A more detailed quantification and distribution including residual inter-story drifts and residual global deformations will be obtained from forthcoming 3D nonlinear dynamic analyses.

The nonlinear static analyses of CDRLF structures showed bilinear capacity curves with a linear ascending tendency in the post yield region, as can be seen in Fig. 3a, 3b and Fig. 4. This particular shape of the capacity curve can be explained by examining the shape of the individual pushover curves of the two subsystems. As can be observed in Fig. 4, the link frames are characterised by elastic-plastic behaviour, while the coupling beam frames are characterised by a fully elastic response even after the NC target displacement, which is also confirmed by the state of the CDRLF structures shown in Fig. 3c, 3d. In contrast to the MRF's (which are difficult and/or expensive to repair) and DRLF's (which can be repaired by replacing the dissipative links, but there is no re-centring capability), the CDRLF's have an improved seismic performance as these contain both qualities: Reparability (by replacing the yielded links) and re-centring capability (provided by the coupling beam frames).

Fig. 3. Capacity curves (a-b) and global plastic mechanisms at NC seismic intensity level (c-d)

Fig. 4. Capacity curves of 4- and 8-story CDRLF's and their corresponding subsystems

4 Conclusions

In this paper the basic concept of the DRLF and CDRLF was introduced and demonstrated by applying it to the design of a typical low- and mid-rise office building. The case study included also two MRF's. The steel consumption (excluding connections) corresponding to the construction of the investigated 4-story structures was: ▪ *MRF_4* (123 tons); ▪ *DRLF_4* (133 tons / >8%); ▪ *CDRLF_4* (139 tons / >13%). In case of the 8-story structures, the steel consumption was: ▪ *MRF_8* (250 tons); ▪ *DRLF_8* (296 tons / >19%); ▪ *CDRLF_8* (298 tons / >19%). Consequently, the MRF's were characterised by a lower steel consumption. However, it is to be noted that the column bases for MRF's were fixed, while they were pinned for the other two structures – which

leads to lower costs for the foundations. All three structural configurations showed a favourable seismic performance, with the basic code requirements being fulfilled. However, the DRLF's are moreover repairable after a strong seismic event (i.e. link replacement), while the CDRLF's have the possibility of being repaired and additionally possess a re-centring capability (provided by coupling beam frames). Both aspects are associated with superior seismic performance and higher resilience.

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